

RECOVERING RIGID CELLULAR FOAM MATERIAL FROM END-OF-LIFE WIND TURBINE BLADES

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Keywords: Wind Turbine Blades, Mechanical recycling, Foam recovery, Material quality, Sink-float

Abstract

This study addresses the challenge of recycling wind turbine blades, particularly focusing on the mechanical extraction of foam material from the blade's sandwich structure. With the impending ban on landfilling in Europe by 2025, the wind industry is compelled to find sustainable solutions for decommissioned blades. Mechanical recycling, involving shredding and sorting techniques, emerges as a cost-effective method for waste treatment.

The research employs both laboratory and industrial-scale experiments to assess the feasibility of foam extraction. Shredding processes, coupled with sink-float separation techniques, effectively separate foam from composite materials. Quality assessment procedures, including density estimation, Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), confirm the purity of the recovered foam material.

Results indicate successful foam recovery with minimal impurities, as evidenced by consistent density values and chemical analyses revealing a PVC composition. SEM images depict a clean, closed-cell structure typical of PVC foam, further validating the recycling process's efficacy.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates the mechanical extraction of foam from wind turbine blades, offering a promising avenue for sustainable waste management in the wind energy sector.

1. Introduction

Today, the wind turbines that were installed in the 90s are reaching the end of their lives, which is between 20 - 25 years. Although wind turbines are 85 % - 90 % recyclable, the blades pose a great challenge as they consist of thermoset composite materials. The blade's waste treatment method that currently prevails is landfilling. However, the impending ban of landfilling in Europe by 2025 [1], underscores the European Wind Industry's commitment towards reuse, recover or recycle 100% of the decommissioned blades. Recycling techniques for blades primarily fall within three categories: Mechanical, Chemical, or Thermal recycling. All these methods focus on fiber recovery from end-of-life blades, as most of their mass consists of FRPs (Fiber Reinforced Polymers) [2].

This paper focuses on Mechanical recycling of the forthcoming blade waste as it is a simple and cost-effective method of waste treatment. Mechanical recycling is based on the size reduction of waste by cutting, shredding, crushing and grinding techniques in dimensions that depend on the intended

application of the material. Mechanical methods are also used to pre-process materials for other methods such as Thermal and Chemical recycling. The granulated mixture is sorted into different parts using sieves, air or water-based techniques.

From mechanically recycling the FRP part of the blades, the fibers are recovered, while the resin and other material residues are typically used in the production of alternative fuels [3]. Although an ample studies on the potential applications of recycled fibers can be found in the literature, there have been limited industrial applications of mechanically recovered fibers. In Finland the company Conenor manufactures thermoplastic composites from shredded composites and wood, which can be used as core material for hollow decking boards or multilayer solid boards. In Denmark two companies, Miljøskærm and G-fiber produce sound insulation panels. Finally, in the USA Global Fiberglass Solution makes composites for railroad and subway ties, yard rails, jersey barriers, bollards and utility poles [2].

Limited literature focuses on extracting materials other than fibers from end-of-life blades. However, some studies explore the mechanical recycling of blade waste, such as P. Meinschmidt in [4], recycling balsa wood from a wind turbine rotor blade for reuse in insulation board production. Another study of Corvaglia et al [5] analyzes the procedure of recycling polypropylene (PP)-based sandwich panels by converting them into short fiber composite material.

In this study we utilize mechanical treatment, specifically shredding, to process end-of-life wind turbine blades with the objective to evaluate the feasibility of extracting rigid cellular foam material. The material undergoes rigorous experimental analysis for its identification.

2. Materials and Methods

Two pieces from the tip of a 20m blade were used as samples and are presented in **Figure 1a**. The sandwich part of the structure, highlighted from its green color, consists of FRP skins and foam core material, as illustrated in **Figure 1b**. The rest of the structure consists of the same skin material, mostly biaxial or triaxial glass reinforcements impregnated with an unknown resin.

Figure 1. (a) The blade pieces, (b) The sandwich part of the blade, (c) The shredding process of the sandwich part.

Mechanical shredding was employed to separate the cellular foam from the FRP skin, accompanied by a sink-float technique to sort the collected fragments.

2.1. Fine Shredder

Two experiments were conducted at different scales, one on a laboratory and the other on an industrial scale. In both cases, similar technology shredders were used, consisting of a rotating cylinder with protruding parts and a sieve positioned underneath. When the sandwich pieces of the blade are introduced into the shredder, they are crushed between its cylinder and the surrounding chamber walls. The developing shear stresses on their surface result in skin detachment, as shown in **Figure 1c**.

2.2. Sink Float Separation Technique

The sink-float technique utilizes water to separate materials of different densities. In this case the large difference in the density of foam 80 kg/m^3 , water $1,000 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and FRP composite $2,400 \text{ kg/m}^3$ facilitates effective separation. During both scale experiments, the collected fragments obtained from the shredding process were added in a beaker filled with water. Then the mixture was stirred to enable the separation of pieces with different densities. Lighter pieces, having a density lower than that of water, floated to the surface, while denser pieces sank to the bottom.

2.3. Experiments

2.3.1. Small Scale Experiment

This experiment was conducted in a laboratory and aimed to assess the feasibility of skin detachment from the sandwich part of an end-of-life blade. This process utilized the shredding machine, as depicted on the left of **Figure 2**. It consisted of an air filter on top, necessary due to the glass fibers dust that rises during the shredding procedure; and a sieve underneath with holes of 4mm dimensions.

Figure 2. The small- (left) and large-scale (right) fine shredders.

The left piece of **Figure 1a** was cut to reduce in size and fed to the shredder. Trials with different time fractions during the shredding process were conducted, aiming to optimize the shredding procedure and achieve fragments of the desired dimensions suitable for the sink float separation technique.

For the sink-float separation, a beaker was filled with water. Subsequently, the shredded fragments were added. The mixture was then mixed into pieces with different densities to be separated. The floating and sinking materials were recovered separately using a plastic scoop.

2.3.2. Large Scale Experiment

This experiment represented an industrial-scale upscaling of the smaller laboratory-scale experiment. An industrial fine shredder, illustrated on the right of **Figure 2**, comprising a rotating cylinder with protruding components akin to the smaller-scale shredder, was utilized, along with a sieve underneath featuring holes of a few centimeters in dimensions.

The right blade piece of **Figure 1a** underwent shredding, and the resulting fragments were transported to the laboratory for sink float separation. Following shredding, the pieces were categorized by size using two sieves with varying hole dimensions. The foam fragment samples were then added to a beaker with water to be separated utilizing the sink float technique. The floating and the sinking materials were gathered for further analysis and the water was carefully disposed.

2.4. Quality Assessment

The collected sinking and floating samples were subjected to three different quality evaluation experiments aiming to identify the recovered foam material.

2.4.1. Density Estimation

To investigate the amount of resin residues from the adjacent laminates after the mechanical separation, six foam pieces from the large-scale experiment were cut into cubes by a scalpel and were used as samples. The specimens were left to dry in a laboratory room environment before scaling for more than two weeks after the sink-float separation.

Their dimensions were measured using a caliper, followed by weighing on a high-precision scale. From the dimensions measurements each sample's volume V (Eq. 1) was estimated with its respective uncertainty. The uncertainty of the Volume function was derived through the propagation of errors in both mass and dimension standard deviations.

$$V = x \times y \times z. \quad (1)$$

Then the density ρ of each piece was estimated by the equation (Eq. 2), along with its associated uncertainty calculated through error propagation. The average foam density value was then computed, and the standard percentage deviation of each piece was determined.

$$\rho = V/m. \quad (2)$$

The aim was to examine the match of the measured density property with foam values, know from the market, used in the wind turbine blade manufacturing e.g., 60kg/m^3 or 80kg/m^3 , while considering the deviation of the samples weight from their mean value which could indicate for filled cells with resin at the foam surface open cells, when substantially varying.

2.4.2. Attenuated Total Reflectance -Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR)

The Bruker Alpha II instrument was used for characterizing the foam material, equipped with the Platinum-ATR module, utilizing a single reflection Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR) configuration featuring a monolithic diamond crystal. The absorbance method was applied across a spectral range spanning 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} , employing a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , and acquiring 16 scans per sample. The samples were measured as received after drying at 100 C for 4h. Three thin, small chunks of the recovered dried foam were used for the Infrared Spectroscopy. The goal was to correlate the recorded wavenumber signatures of the recovered foam with a signature of a known material to identify it.

2.4.3. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM analysis was carried out on the surface of the specimens, by employing a SEM JSM 6390 equipped with EDS analysis. SEM analysis was subsequently performed on the same samples used for the ATR-FTIR spectroscopy.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Experiment Results

3.1.1. Small Scale Experiment

The small-scale experiment results are summarized in **Figure 3**. **Picture 3a** shows the shredded pieces successfully separated between the skin and foam components. From the sink-float technique results on **Pictures 3b** and **3c**, it is evident that the foam has surfaced atop the beaker, while the skin has settled at the bottom.

Figure 3. The sample collected from the shredder (a.) and the sink-float results (b. and c.).

3.1.2. Large Scale Experiment

The large-scale experiment results are illustrated in **Figure 4**. In **Picture 4a** the shredded fragments are displayed, while **Picture 4b** depicts the sorted sample collected using a manual sieve procedure. The sink-float separation process of the samples is illustrated in **Pictures 4c** and **4d**. In **Picture 4c**, the clear distinction between green foam pieces and beige skin pieces is evident, with the foam floating and the skin sinking to the bottom. In **Picture 4d**, among the floating pieces, a foam piece with remnants of skin can be observed.

Figure 4. From the left to the right is shown the process of separating the shredded blade materials. The fragments are sorted through sieves and then the sink-float separation results are presented.

Overall, the steps followed for foam recovery were shredding the blade sample, sorting the fragments using sieves and then utilizing a sink-float technique to separate foam from skin pieces. The process was successful with most of the foam pieces floating and almost all laminates sinking in the bottom. However, instances of pieces featuring both foam and laminate, either floating or sinking, were observed. It's essential to note that mechanical treatment through blade shredding may not achieve 100% effectiveness, leading to a certain percentage of hybrid pieces. The portion of these pieces can be decreased by optimizing the shredding procedure to maximize laminate separation. Therefore, it is substantial to feed with lot of material into the shredder, to enhance the separation through collision and shearing, while selecting the appropriate sieve grid size to control the geometry of the outcoming material.

3.2. Quality Assessment Results

3.2.1. Density Estimation

The Density experiment results are presented in **Table 1**. The pieces show an average density of 81.6 kg/m³, with a corresponding uncertainty of 5.4%. This value agrees with the density obtained from literature of 80 kg/m³. This means that the recovered foam is pure and has no significant impurities or resin-skin remnants. The density value of 110 kg/m³ was significantly higher than the rest of the foam density results and was therefore excluded from the average value estimation. This can be attributed to possible impurities or water absorption during the sink float separation process.

Table 1. Density calculations for each piece with respective percentage deviation and mean values.

Density Calculations		ρ_{mean} (kg/m ³)	$\delta\rho_{\text{mean}}$ (%)
ρ (kg/m ³)	uncert. $\delta\rho$ (%)		
83.5	7.2	81.6	5.4
88.1	2.4		
110.0	3.2		
79.3	4.7		
80.4	2.5		
76.6	2.6		

3.2.2. ATR-FTIR Results

The wavenumber spectrum derived through the Infrared Spectroscopy is presented in the **Figure 5**. The characteristic peaks of the PVC and its additives (610, 633, 678, 757, 811, 853, 917, 960, 1018, 1103, 1180, 1230, 1306, 1410, 1426, 1507, 1536, 1594, 1705, 2852, 2920, 3334, 3376) were identified [7-11], some of them are listed in **Table 2**. The correlation to an existing dataset from a given PVC spectrum was not obvious due to ample of peaks presence, e.g., between 500-1000 cm⁻¹ and between 1500-1700 cm⁻¹ which were not found elsewhere in the literature.

Table 2. Assignment of the principal bands of PVC [11].

Wavenumbers (cm ⁻¹)	Assignment
2912	stretching C-H of CH ₂
1435 – 1427	deform. (Wagg) of CH ₂
1331 – 1255	deform. C-H of CHCl
1099	Stretching C-C
966	Rocking CH ₂
637	Stretching C-Cl

Figure 5. ATR-FTIR spectrum of the recovered foam after drying.

3.2.3. SEM Results

The scanning revealed a rigid foam cell type of a closed form, having a round-like cross sections with a diameter of approximately 250µm, see **Figure 6**. The cells seem to be empty of any type of rests in them, i.e., resin or fibers. Through several local analysis (more than three measurements) on the foam surface, SEM analysis revealed the composition of the material, listed in the **Table 3**. The Chloride presence, in combination with the ATR-FTIR, indicates that the foam core is a Polyvinylchloride version (PVC).

Table 3. Weight distribution of the foam constitutive elements

Element	Cl K	O K	C K	Total
%	29.13	10.81	60.06	100.0

Figure 6. SEM image of the recovered foam after drying (left) and typical local spectrum analysis.

4. Conclusions

The conducted research has conclusively demonstrated the feasibility of mechanically extracting foam from the sandwich part of end-of-life wind turbine blades. This was achieved through a mechanical waste treatment process, initially tested and optimized in the lab and subsequently implemented on an industrial scale. Two step procedure was deployed, involving cutting of the blade parts in smaller pieces before shredding. The collected fragments underwent sorting using sieves and a sink float separation technique.

The successfully recovered foam material underwent rigorous quality evaluation. Initially, Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analyses were conducted to identify the foam material, which was determined to be a PVC version. The SEM results indicated a clean, closed-cell surface structure, consistent with PVC, and chemical analysis confirmed its PVC composition. The FTIR analysis corroborated these findings, supporting the hypothesis that the foam indeed consists of PVC and contains no resin residues. The absence of resin remnants was additionally supported by density calculation results, aligning with expected values obtained from literature sources.

Acknowledgments

We acknowledge Polyeco S.A. and GK-Recycling who provided access to their facilities and equipment, as well as invaluable assistance during the material mechanical process. We also acknowledge Professor Stamatina Vougiouka of the National Technical University of Athens for providing access to the Polymer Technology Laboratory and the FTIR equipment, Dr. Christos Zotiadis for conducting the FTIR tests and Dr. Kostantinos Anastatiadis for his helpful consulting on the evaluation of the results.

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